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Technical Paper:

Machine-learning-based fatigue life prediction of metal components subjected to block loading

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Accurate lifetime prediction of metal components subjected to cyclic loading remains challenging. Many analytical, (non)linear fatigue damage accumulation models have been developed since the Palmgren–Miner rule was first presented. Analytical models are often strongly biased towards particular datasets and limited by simplifications and assumptions. Machine learning, however, offers a promising solution by learning relationships directly from the data without human bias. In this work, 13 different machine learning models are trained for fatigue life prediction of metal components subjected to block loading. The number of high-quality datasets in literature was rather limited, hence nearly 160 fatigue experiments were performed to improve the training set. A comparison study is performed to determine the best-performing machine learning model. Finally, the best performing models are compared to Miner's rule. The results show that the machine learning models consistently outperform Miner's rule.

Keywords: Metal fatigue, Machine learning, Damage accumulation, Life prediction.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue damage is one of the most common reasons for the engineering failures of metal components and structures across many industries. For over a century, researchers have been developing fatigue damage accumulation models based on empirical observations or on theories derived thereof. Such models aim to estimate the fatigue life of a component subjected to variable amplitude cyclic loading. The linear damage accumulation rule (LDR) developed by Palmgren and Miner [1] is the most widely used model. Due to its inherent linearity, fatigue life estimations obtained with the LDR can be extremely conservative, or even non-conservative up to a factor 10 [2]. Many nonlinear damage models have been developed [3], yet none have been universally accepted. They only account for a limited number of phenomenological factors, which limits their effectiveness to specific materials and loading conditions [4],[5].

Data-driven models can describe highly nonlinear relationships, which has made them popular for the prediction of fatigue strength and other mechanical properties. Gautham et al. [6] were the first to investigate data-driven methods to predict fatigue strength. They used a database comprising 450 constant amplitude fatigue experiments of 20 different steels. Their model predicted the experimental fatigue strength within

a 10% error band. Agrawal et al. [7] recognized the potential of this approach and decided to explore it further. They investigated the use of feature selection in combination with regression methods such as polynomial regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), neural networks and decision trees. They achieved R^2 values higher than 0.95 when predicting fatigue strength with support vector machines (SVM) and variations of decision trees. Agrawal et al. [8] continued to build on their previous research by comparing 40 supervised machine learning models to each other. They employed advanced ensemble modeling techniques to develop a high-performance model which forms the basis of an open-access online web-tool called the 'Steel Fatigue Strength Predictor'. The work of Agrawal et al. has been a basis for multiple other research studies on data-driven prediction of material properties [9]–[11] and constant amplitude fatigue lives, e.g. [12]–[16]. For a more detailed overview of machine learning for materials science, the reader is referred to the review paper of Sparks et al. [17].

Data driven methods have proven to be powerful for modelling the fatigue strength and estimating fatigue life of various materials subjected to constant amplitude loading. However, research on the use of data-driven methods for fatigue life estimation of metals subjected to variable amplitude fatigue ([18]–[21]) is very limited. Most papers are limited to two-level block loading, the simplest form of variable amplitude loading and others (e.g. [20]) only consider a very small set of multi-level block loading experiments. One of the primary reasons is that the use of data-driven methods for fatigue life prediction is hindered considerably by the sparsity of experimental data in open literature. This was addressed in a previous work by the authors of this paper [22], where an open-access dataset of variable amplitude fatigue experiments was presented.

To train the selected models, a large database of experiments was collected from literature. This database was extended with the dataset obtained by the authors in [22]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the resulting block-loading fatigue database is the largest and most complete one to date. This database was used to train various machine learning models, which involves data preprocessing, model training, tuning, and finally performance evaluation. Finally, it is determined which of the considered machine learning models performs best for fatigue life prediction of components subjected to block-loading spectra.

MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

In the context of fatigue life predictions, the model should be capable of predicting numerical values. Therefore, a supervised machine learning (ML) model suitable for regression tasks is necessary. It was decided to limit the scope of this work to 'popular' ML models that are readily available as open-source Python routines. Most models that are considered in this work have been implemented in scikit-learn, a machine learning library for the Python programming language [23]. This study includes the following models: Ridge & Lasso Regression, Polynomial Regression, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest (RF) & Extra Trees (ET), Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR) and Symbolic Regression (SR). For an overview of these models reference is made to the scikit-learn documentation [23].

EXPERIMENT DATABASE

As mentioned in the introduction, within the context of variable amplitude fatigue life prediction using machine learning, only two-level block loading predictions are reported in literature as of today. The most influential features generally are the cycles to failure N , for the first stress level, the applied cycles in the first block n_1 , the cycles to failure N_2 for the second stress level, and the stress amplitudes. The use of machine learning for multi-level block loading life prediction would be a significant jump in research. The main reason why this has not yet been done is the lack of a representative dataset.

The performance of machine learning models depends on both the quantity and quality of the training data.

A higher-quality training dataset requires a lower quantity of training data to achieve good results. A database is established based on data acquired from literature and experiments previously performed by the authors. It contains results of 969 block loading experiments in total, of which 833 two-level block loading and 136 multi-level (three or more level) block loadings. The database covers 26 different materials. Table 1 shows an overview of the datasets included in the database. Four block loading types are distinguished, High-Low (H-L), Low-High (L-H), multi-level (ML) and repeated two-level block loading. They are illustrated in Figure 1. In H-L loading, specimens are first subjected to stress amplitude S_{a1} for n_1 cycles and then subjected to a lower stress amplitude S_{a2} for n_{exp} cycles until failure. For multi-level loading, the specimens are first subjected to more than two different stress amplitudes before failure. In repeated two-level block loading experiments, an H-L or L-H sequence with a predefined number of cycles in each block is chosen. The chosen H-L or L-H sequence is then repeated until the specimen fails. Finally, there are also experiments with a fully random loading sequence. In this work, the choice was made to exclude stochastic loading sequences as the number of these experiments with respect to the size of the database is very limited. Nonetheless, for the sake of completeness, it is mentioned in Table 1 if one of the datasets does contain this type of data. Only experiment datasets where constant amplitude fatigue lives were reported could be used since this material data is required as input for the models. The database contains a variety of experiment types (rotating bending, axial fatigue, ...); for detailed information the reader is referred to the references in Table 1 and the open-access material database [24] where all the experiments have been collected.

Figure 1: The different block loading sequence types in the experiment database.

Source	Material(s)	Loading Type
Rey et al. [25]	SAE 4130 Alloy	H-L, L-H, ML
Liu and Corten [27]	Al2024-T4 Al7075-T6 Hard-drawn steel	Repeated two-level block loading
Spitzer and Corten [29]	Al7075-T6	Al7075-T6 Repeated two-level block loading
Manson et al. [31]	AISI 4130 AISI E52100 AISI 304 ELC Al5456-H311	H-L
Manson et al. [33]	300CVM SAE 4130 (Soft) SAE4130 (Hard)	H-L, L-H, two-level alternating block loading
Manson and Halford [35]	Ti-6Al-4V D.T.D. 683	H-L, L-H, ML
Palin-Luc (1996)	GS61 spheroidal graphite cast-iron	H-L, L-H
Shang and Yao [38]	C45 16Mn hot-rolled 16Mn normalized	H-L, L-H
Pavlou [40]	Al2024-T42	H-L, L-H
Jin [42]	Ti-6Al-4V	H-L, L-H

Source	Material(s)	Loading Type
Dattoma et al. [26]	30NiCrMoV12	H-L, L-H, ML
Zhao and Jiang [28]	Al7075-T651	H-L
Pereira [30]	P355NL1	H-L, L-H
Colin and Fatemi [32]	AISI 304 ELC Al7075-T6	H-L, L-H, Random
Zhu et al. [34]	41Cr4 C45	ML
Aid et al. [36]	Al6082-T6	H-L, L-H, ML, Random
Peng [37]	30CrMnSiA	H-L, L-H
Zhu et al. [39]	P355NL1	H-L, L-H
Gao et al. [41]	C35 P355NL1 Q235B 41Cr4	H-L, L-H, ML
Hectors et al. [22]	S275	H-L, L-H, ML

Table 1: Overview of block loading experiment datasets used to construct the experiment database that is used as training data for the machine learning models.

TWO-LEVEL BLOCK LOADING

Data preprocessing

Data quality significantly impacts model performance. Datapoints with missing values especially. Hence, all datapoints with missing values were removed from the database prior to model training. In addition, only high-cycle fatigue behavior is considered, therefore any datapoint with n_1 or n_2 values lower than 500 cycles was not considered. Finally, any features still containing NaN values are removed from the dataset. This results in a dataframe of 375 data points with each 15 features. These features are reported in Table 2.

To ensure that the training data is of high quality, outliers

are removed since they can adversely affect model performance. In this work, the outliers were filtered out based on the Z-score which measures exactly how many standard deviations above or below the mean a data point is. Data points with a Z-score greater than 3.0 (for features n_1 and n_2) are removed, i.e. all data points for which n_1 or n_2 deviate more than 3 times the standard deviation from the mean. The resulting dataset contains 354 data points. To build an effective model, it is crucial to select features with strong correlations to the target variable n_2 . The data correlation was investigated using Pearson's correlation coefficient, which measures the linear association between features. Figure 2 presents the correlation matrix for two-level block loading data. The features N_1 , N_2 , and n_1 have the highest positive correlation with the target variable n_2 . Notably, S_{a2} exhibits the highest negative correlation.

Feature(s)	Definition
E	Young's Modulus [GPa]
UTS	Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]
C, Mn, P, S, Si	Weight percentages of C, Mn, P, S and Si
S_{ai}	Stress amplitude in the i_{th} loading block
n_i	Number of cycles in the i_{th} loading block
R_i	Stress ratio in the i_{th} loading block
N_i	Total number of cycles to failure at a constant amplitude stress S_{ai} at the i_{th} loading block

Table 2: Remaining features after pre-processing of the data obtained from the literature.

Further analysis was conducted using Spearman's correlation. Here, input features, N_2 , C, and N_1 showed the highest positive correlation, while S_{a2} , UTS, and S_{a1} exhibited the highest negative correlation. The stress ratios and chemical composition features had only weak correlations with the target variable n_2 . To identify potential nonlinear dependencies, mutual information regression was performed. The analysis revealed that features such as N_2 , S_{a2} , N_1 , S_{a1} , and UTS shared the most mutual information with the target variable n_2 . On the other hand, the stress ratios showed minimal relation to the target variable, and n_1 exhibited only a small amount of mutual information, contrary to physical expectations. Based on data correlation and recursive feature elimination, the most important features were determined to be: N_1 , S_{a1} , n_1 , N_2 , S_{a2} and UTS.

The results suggest that the stress ratios R_1 and R_2 have almost no dependency with the target variable. This can be attributed to the fact that most of the stress ratios in

the database have a value of -1, resulting in a very low level of variation in this feature. This uniformity leads to a biased correlation between the stress ratios and target variable, resulting in a weak or non-existent relationship between them. Furthermore, with the purpose to improve model's performance, seven new features were engineered based on domain knowledge:

(1) n_1/N_1 : The cycle ratio, calculated as the ratio of the applied number of cycles n_1 to the number of cycles to failure N_1 at stress amplitude S_{a1} . The cycle ratio is the fundamental basis of most analytical models (e.g. Miner's rule).

(2) S_{a2}/S_{a1} : The stress amplitude ratio indicates the type of loading transition. If this feature has a value smaller than 1, it means that the loading sequence is high-low. If this feature is greater than 1, it is a low-high loading sequence. The loading sequence has a significant impact on fatigue life.

Figure 2: Pearson correlation matrix for two-level block loading data.

(3) **E/UTS**: The material's strength-to-stiffness ratio. It is a dimensionless number.

(4) **N_{last}** : This feature corresponds to the number of cycles to failure for the stress amplitude of the last block of the loading history.

(5) **n_{exp}** : This feature represents the remaining fatigue life for the last loading block reported in the experimental dataset.

(6) **D_{miner}** : This feature represents the theoretical initial damage according to Miner's rule, which is calculated as the sum of the cycle ratios before the last block, as shown in Equation (1). It represents the accumulated damage prior to the last loading block.

$$D_{Miner} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N-1} \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (1)$$

(7) **D_{DCA}** : Initial damage based on damage curve approach (DCA) of Manson and Halford [35]. It takes the loading sequence effect into account and it only uses the applied cycles n_i and cycles to failure N_i . The initial damage D_{DCA} is calculated with Equation (2) by excluding the last loading block.

$$D_{DCA} = \left[\left(\frac{n_1}{N_1} \right)^{\alpha_{1,2}} + \frac{n_2}{N_2} \right]^{\alpha_{2,3}} + \dots + \frac{n_{i-1}}{N_{i-1}} \right]^{\alpha_{i-1,i}} \quad \text{with } \alpha_{i-1,i} = \left(\frac{N_{i-1}}{N_i} \right)^{0.4} \quad (2)$$

The last four features have the benefit of being applicable to multi-level block loading predictions, which makes them very valuable to use for both two- and multi-level machine-learning-based predictions.

To ensure consistent scaling of the input features, standardization is applied to all dataframes in this work. Standardization scales the data by accounting for mean and standard deviation, facilitating the training process of machine learning models. In the end, six different preprocessed dataframes are created. These will be used for training and evaluating the machine learning models. Each dataframe contains 354 data points, but differs in the number of features included. Table 3 provides an overview of these six dataframes.

Model training & tuning

Model training and tuning is a critical step in the machine learning workflow where the model is fit to the training

set and hyperparameters are adjusted to achieve optimal performance and accuracy. Each of the models described in the previous section is evaluated for its capabilities of predicting fatigue life under block loading. In total 13 models are evaluated: Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Lasso and Ridge Regression, Polynomial Regression, Extra Trees (ET), AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR), Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression (XGBR), Bayesian Ridge Regression, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Symbolic Regression (SR). Furthermore, a voting regression is employed to combine predictions from the top three models, improving generalization and robustness [8].

The hyperparameters of the considered models were tuned using a random search algorithm with 10-fold cross-validation. The algorithm explores a predefined search space in 90 iterations and identifies the top 5% combinations of hyperparameters with a 99% probability. Prior to training the models, the data from the dataframes is split into training and test sets using an 80%–20% split. This ensures that the models are trained on a sufficiently large dataset, while still having a good amount of data for testing and evaluation [8].

Since the test set only contains 20% of the total dataset, the optimal fit often requires fewer estimators. Nevertheless, the discrepancy between the best scores on the training and test sets were found to be small.

Model evaluation

The R^2 and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) metrics are used to assess model performance. The MAE represents errors in the same unit as the target variable, while being less influenced by outliers than R^2 . All the models studied in this work were trained on each of the datasets reported in Table 3. Figure 3 shows an overview of the model performances for the models trained on the different dataframes. Overall the ET, KNN and GBR exhibit the highest accuracy. The KNN model performs better for dataframes with engineered features. The KNN model is affected by the curse of dimensionality, i.e. high-dimensional data is detrimental to its performance. The general impression is that feature engineering improves the performance of the models. The linear-regression-based models (e.g., Ridge, Lasso, polynomial and Bayesian regression), the SVR and the SR model are the worst-performing models.

As mentioned in the introduction, Agrawal et al. [8] demonstrated that combining the best performing models using a voting regressor improves the prediction accuracy. Hence, for each dataframe, a voting regressor

Dataframe	Features
df1	$C, Mn, P, S, Si, E, UTS, N1, Sa1, n1, N2, Sa2, R1, R2$
df2	$UTS, N1, Sa1, n1, N2, Sa2$
df3	$E/UTS, n1/N1, Sa2/Sa1, E, UTS, N1, Sa1, n1, N2, Sa2$
df4	$E/UTS, n1/N1, Sa2/Sa1, N2$
df5	$E/UTS, Sa2/Sa1, D_{miner}, N_{last}$
df6	$E/UTS, Sa2/Sa1, D_{DCA}, N_{last}$

Table 3: Overview of dataframes used as input for two-level block loading predictions.

Figure 3: R^2 for all models trained on each dataframe for the two-level block loading dataset.

was constructed based on the three best-performing models. The performance of the voting regressor trained on the six different dataframes is presented in Figure 4. The performance of the voting regressors was found to be slightly better than the best-performing 'conventional' model. The voting regressors improve both the R^2 and MAE compared to the ET.

Considering both Figure 3 and Figure 4, it can be observed that the 'conventional' models and the voting regressors trained on dataframe 6 perform best. Dataframe 6 introduces the feature D_{DCA} . This indicates that introducing some prior information on the effect of load interaction effects could lead to better prediction results. The fact that the models trained on dataframe 6 perform better than those trained on dataframe 5, with

feature D_{miner} , could be expected since the DCA generally outperforms Miner's rule for two-level block loading [4],[22]. Figure 5 shows a plot of the predicted versus experimental values for each voting regressor trained on each dataframe for the two-level block loading dataset. It shows that the majority of the model predictions lie within a 50% error band around the mean.

MULTI-LEVEL BLOCK LOADING

Data preparation

Most data preparation steps are analogous to the steps for two-level block loading. In this case, in addition to the two-level block loading data, 136 multi-level block

Figure 4: R^2 (blue, left vertical axis) and MAE (red, right vertical axis) for each voting regressor trained on each dataframe for the two-level block loading dataset.

Figure 5: Predicted vs experimental values for each voting regressor trained on each dataframe for the two-level block loading dataset.

loading experiments are added to the dataset. The added data comprises 34 three-level, 11 four-level, 9 five-level, 2 eight-level block loading experiments and 80 two-level repeated block loading experiments. Dataframes are created that either contain up to three-level block loading (e.g. df3 in Table 4) or up to five-level block loading (e.g. df6 in Table 4). These dataframes are reported in Table 4.

Dataframes 3 and 6 contain stress amplitude, applied number of cycles and cycles to failure data for each block. Zero-padding was applied to these dataframes. This is a data preprocessing technique commonly used to handle situations where some features may not be available for certain data points.

Model evaluation

Figure 6 shows the R^2 for the models trained each of the dataframes. It can be seen that ET, GBR and XGBR are the best-performing models. Similar to how it was discussed in the previous section, these three models were combined to build a voting regressor. However, in this case the voting regressor did not always outperform the conventional machine learning models. Out of all

models, SR and Bayesian linear regression perform the worst.

A voting regressor was constructed with the three best performing models for each dataframe. The performance of each voting regressor is visualized in Figure 7. Overall, the performance for the models trained on the dataframes with D_{miner} or D_{DCA} is worse than for the ones with zero-padding. The models trained on the dataframe with D_{miner} exhibit the highest MAE. Figure 7 also shows that the performance of the models for multi-level block loading, trained on dataframes containing five-level block loading data, is better than that of those trained on dataframes containing only two- and three-level block loading experiments. This could be an indicator that the interaction effects observed in two-level block loading experiments do not contain sufficient information for the development of multi-level block loading models (both analytical and data-driven). Hence, strengthening the conclusions made in [22] that future experimental research should focus on multi-level block loading compared to two-level block loading. In addition, researchers should be encouraged to publish multi-level block loading experiment datasets in open-access literature.

Dataframe	Features
df1	$E/UTS, S_{a2}/S_{a1}, D_{miner}, N_{last}$
df2	$E/UTS, S_{a2}/S_{a1}, D_{DCA}, N_{last}$
df3	$E/UTS, n_1, N_1, S_{a1}, n_2, N_2, S_{a2}, N_3, S_{a3}$
df4	$E/UTS, S_{a2}/S_{a1}, D_{miner}, N_{last}$
df5	$E/UTS, S_{a2}/S_{a1}, D_{DCA}, N_{last}$
df6	$E/UTS, n_1, N_1, S_{a1}, n_2, N_2, S_{a2}, n_3, N_3, S_{a3}, n_4, N_4, S_{a4}, n_5, N_5, S_{a5}$

Table 4: Overview of dataframes used as input for multi-level block loading predictions.

Figure 6: R^2 for all models trained on each dataframe for the multi-level block loading dataset.

Figure 7: R^2 (blue, left vertical axis) and MAE (red, right vertical axis) for each voting regressor trained on each dataframe for the multi-level block loading dataset.

Comparison of Figures 4 and 7 shows that the machine learning models perform better for the two-level block loading than for multi-level block loading. This is because the number of multi-level block loading experiments in the database is significantly smaller. In addition, the similarity between two-level block loading experiments and multi-level block loading experiments diminishes as the number of blocks increases and as such also the training value of the two-level block loading experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the use of machine learning models for fatigue life prediction of metal components

subjected to block-loading. Tree-based models, such as Random Forest, Extra Trees, Gradient Boosting Regressor, and Extreme Gradient Boosting Regressor, emerged as the best-performing models. These were also combined in a voting regressor for both two-level and multi-level block loading predictions. In most cases the voting regressor outperformed the other models. Additionally, the feasibility of applying a two-level machine learning model for multi-level block loading predictions was explored. It was found that, despite the limited amount of data, the machine learning models successfully learned patterns that can be generalized to multi-level block loading predictions. The use of analytical models for introducing prior knowledge could be observed to have a positive influence, however this should be re-evaluated as more experimental data becomes available.

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